

Getting Started with QualCoder AI Features

This guide walks you through setting up QualCoder with local AI support using Llama 3.1. While QualCoder integrates with multiple AI models, we selected Llama 3.1 available through the [Ollama wrapper](#), which is free, open source, and runs entirely on your local machine. This setup ensures that no data is sent externally or used to train the model, making it particularly well suited for research involving human subjects, especially when working with sensitive data.

Disclaimer: The latest version of QualCoder requires macOS Sequoia or later. Please check [QualCoder requirements](#) and note that the AI integration may not perform as expected on all systems. Prompts or queries may occasionally time out. Performance can be affected by factors such as hardware configuration, available memory, processor capabilities, storage capacity, model size, context window settings, and overall system load.

Download & Install the AI Model

Access the website ollama.com/library/llama3.1:latest. Click “download” in the upper-right corner and select the option for your operating system.

The download is several GB and may take a few minutes. Once the download is complete, follow the steps below:

macOS

1. Open the downloaded .dmg
2. Drag **Ollama** into the **Applications** folder
3. Open **Applications** → **Ollama**
4. If prompted by macOS security, click **Open**
5. Ollama runs in the background (menu bar icon)
6. Open the Terminal and run: `ollama pull llama3.1`
7. Once completed, run the application with the command: `ollama run llama3.1`

Windows

1. Double-click the downloaded .exe
2. Follow the installation wizard
3. Allow firewall access if prompted
4. Ollama starts automatically and runs in the system tray
5. Open the Command Prompt or PowerShell and run: `ollama pull llama3.1`
6. Once completed, run the application with the command: `ollama run llama3.1`

Launch Ollama and test that it is working properly.

Install & Launch QualCoder

Select the [QualCoder version 3.8 release](#) for your operating system and follow the instructions. Note that macOS users will need to manually allow the application to run due to system security settings.

Launch QualCoder and ensure the style is set to **native**, so that the following instructions match the menu options on your computer. You may go to “QualCoder > Preferences...” or “Project > Settings” to make the selection.

Click “ok” and you will be prompted to relaunch QualCoder before you see the change in the style.

Enabling AI in QualCoder

In QualCoder, go to the “AI” tab and select “Settings”.

Enable AI by checking the box and choose llama3.1 from the dropdown menu. No API key is required, as the selected model runs locally.

Before clicking “OK”, go to “Advanced AI options” in the left-lower corner and specify the parameters as shown in the provided configuration below:

- Ensure that you check the option “Send project memo to AI” and “same as UI”
- Select from the drop-down menu “**llama 3.1 latest** for both Large and Fast Model.
- Enter the context window at its maximum capacity for the specified model, which for Llama 3.1 is 128000.
- Click “**OK**”

This should prompt a pop-up with the following message "Since you are using the AI integration for the first time, QualCoder needs to download and install some additional components". Click yes to accept and proceed. The download may take a few minutes.

Time to verify the status: check the lower-left corner of the QualCoder window. If it displays “**AI Ready**”, the setup was successfully completed.

Download the Project Example Folder

During the workshop, we will be experimenting with QualCoder and llama 3.1. We have prepared a project folder containing text files, memos, a codebook, and AI outputs and prompts.

Click the following link to download the example folder: [10.5281/zenodo.18604272](https://zenodo.org/record/105281/files/18604272). Save it in a convenient location on your computer and unzip the folder. With QualCoder open, go to the Project tab. Go to “**Open Project**”, then navigate to and choose the **ucldw2026-ai-demo.qda** folder to start interacting with the project files.

We encourage you to consult QualCoder’s full documentation to learn more about its features, including its AI capabilities: <https://qualcoder-org.github.io/doc/en>.